

Polyhedral Compilation for Multi-dimensional Stream Processing: Addendum

Jakob Leben¹ and George Tzanetakis¹

¹University of Victoria, Department of Computer Science

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Abstract

This is an addendum to the paper Polyhedral Compilation for Multi-dimensional Stream Processing [2]. It contains an extended argument to support the claim that Pluto’s scheduling algorithm likely finds rate-consistent schedules on which our work in [2] depends. Additional experimental results using the GNU C++ compiler are also presented.

1 Pluto and Productive Schedules

The periodic schedule tiling technique presented in [2] requires a productive schedule as input. We discuss why such schedules are likely found by the popular scheduling algorithm in the Pluto optimizer [1]. We claim that Pluto’s optimization objective prioritizes productive schedules above others when the statement dependence graph is connected and in the absence of program parameters. We address program parameters below, but we invite the reader at this moment to abstract them away.

For each schedule dimension, Pluto postulates an upper bound on dependence distances and its objective is to minimize it. In the absence of program parameters, the upper bound is modeled as a single variable and its minimization has the highest priority. Therefore, Pluto will find a schedule with a real upper bound (not infinity) if it exists in its search space. Finally, our claim relies on the following proposition:

Proposition 1.1. *For two dependent statements, there is an upper bound on their dependence distances if and only if their schedule is rate-consistent.*

Proof. We prove Proposition 1.1 as follows:

1. Each access schedule has a single infinite direction (Def. 3.4 Admissible Input in [2]).
2. According to Minkowski-Weyl Theorem, any point in an access schedule is a sum of one of its rays and a point in a bounded polyhedron. For simplicity, assume that this bounded polyhedron is empty, since that does not affect the argument. Then, the access schedule is a cone and each point in it is its ray.
3. Let a ray in an access schedule be $\langle \vec{i}, \vec{t} \rangle$, where \vec{i} is a ray in the array index space, and \vec{t} a ray in the time space. Any point in the access schedule is therefore $\alpha \langle \vec{i}, \vec{t} \rangle$ for some $\alpha \geq 0$.
4. Consider two access schedules for the same array. If they have different infinite directions, they must be equivalent in the \vec{i} component which is a ray of the same array index set. Hence, there exists some common \vec{i} and two possibly different \vec{t} and \vec{t}' so that each point in the first access schedule is $\alpha \langle \vec{i}, \vec{t} \rangle$ and in the second $\beta \langle \vec{i}, \vec{t}' \rangle$.
5. Consider two dependent accesses in two different access schedule - a write and a read of the same array location. They can be expressed as $\gamma \langle \vec{i}, \vec{t} \rangle$ and $\gamma' \langle \vec{i}, \vec{t}' \rangle$.
6. The dependence distance of these two accesses is $\gamma(\vec{t}' - \vec{t})$.

Figure 1: Throughput (vertical, in output elements/ μ s for filter-bank, max-filter, ac, and output elements/ms for wave-1d and wave-2d) in relation to number of threads (horizontal). C++ compiler: Intel (top row) and GNU (bottom row). Algorithm scale: $N = 2000$. Arrp code uses tile sizes in Table 2 in [2]. Arrp and auto-optimized C++ use buffer type 'mask' for all algorithms, except 'shift' for ac. Explicit hoisting and vectorization is enabled for all Arrp sources except for ac. StreamIt results for max-filter are missing due to limitations of the StreamIt compiler.

7. If the infinite directions of the two access schedules are the same (the schedule is rate-consistent), then $\vec{t}' = \vec{t}$ and $\gamma(\vec{t}' - \vec{t}) = 0$.
8. Otherwise, $\vec{t}' \neq \vec{t}$ and $|\gamma(\vec{t}' - \vec{t})|$ grows towards infinity as γ grows towards infinity.
9. Following from 7 and 8, a schedule for two dependent statements with a real upper bound on dependence distances is rate-consistent.

□

While [2] does not give special consideration to programs with parameters, this context deserves it. In the presence of parameters, Pluto models the upper bound on dependence distances using the expression $\vec{u} \cdot \vec{p} + w$ where components of \vec{p} are the parameters. A real upper bound is ensured only when all the components of \vec{u} as well as w are real. However, Pluto performs a multi-objective optimization, minimizing each of the parameter coefficients \vec{u} and w one after another. It is imaginable that minimizing these variables individually forces one of them to infinity. To avoid this, Pluto's algorithm can be modified to minimize the sum $|\vec{u}|_1 + w$ before each individual variable (where $|\vec{u}|_1$ is the L^1 -norm).

2 Additional Experimental Results

Figure 1 is an expansion of Figure 6 in [2] with additional results for the GNU C++ compiler.

References

- [1] BONDHUGULA, U., HARTONO, A., RAMANUJAM, J., AND SADAYAPPAN, P. A practical automatic polyhedral parallelizer and locality optimizer. In *Proceedings of the 29th ACM SIGPLAN Conference on Programming Language Design and Implementation* (New York, NY, USA, 2008), PLDI '08, ACM, pp. 101–113.

- [2] LEBEN, J., AND TZANETAKIS, G. Polyhedral compilation for multi-dimensional stream processing. Manuscript submitted for publication.